

Analysis of Brand Image, Beauty Vlogger, Availability in the Marketplace, Green Product, and Product Benefit on Purchase Decision of Wardah's Day Cream Skincare Product

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Abstract:- This research aims to know the influence of Brand Image, Beauty Vlogger, Availability in the Marketplace, Green Product, and Product Benefit on the Purchase Decision of Wardah's day cream skincare product. The object of this research is generation Z and Millennials women. The populations in this research are young adult women who use Wardah's day cream skincare product located in Jakarta. Sampling was done by Purposive Sampling, with criteria such as young adult women from generation Z and Millennials who are located in Jakarta and use Wardah's day cream skincare product at least once in six months. The sample size is as many as 165 respondents. The Structural Equation Model was chosen as the method of analysis. The results showed that Green Product and Product Benefit have a positive and significant influence on the decision to purchase Wardah's day cream skincare product. Meanwhile, the variables of Brand Image, Beauty Vlogger, and Availability in the marketplace, do not have a significant influence on the decision to purchase Wardah's day cream skincare product. Wardah's management needs to increase the emotional benefits for users of Wardah's day cream skincare product and reposition a strategy in the form of "skincare product can increase individual confidence because they have healthy skin". Apart from that, Wardah's management needs to continue to ensure that the materials for Wardah's day cream skincare product are protected from harmful chemicals such as mercury. Because Indonesian consumers want products that do not contain harmful chemicals to use and do not damage the environment. Suggestions for future researchers are to re-test this research model at different locations and objects of different day cream brands.

Keywords:- Brand Image, Beauty Vlogger, Availability in the Marketplace, Green Product, Product Benefit, Purchase Decision

I. INTRODUCTION

The total population of Indonesia in 2021 is 273 million people, consisting of 135.576.278 (49.5 percent) of females population and 138.303.472 (50.5 percent) of males population (Directorate General of Dukcapil Ministry of Home Affairs, 2021). Based on these data there are 53,923,000 female population aged 15-39 years. This indicates that women aged 15 to 39 years in big cities have a broad social life with high mobility in terms of friends, the world of work, and business. In addition, based on BPS data, there is an increase in the percentage of female formal workers from 2020 of 34.65 percent and 2021 of 36.20 percent (Central Bureau of Statistics, 2021). Women need to pay attention to facial health because it is the most valuable thing to have (Zap Clinic, 2018). Indonesia is a country that has a potential market for beauty products due to lifestyle changes, increased income, and the desire of women to look beautiful. The need for beauty products has become a major need for women today. One of the most consumed beauty products for women in urban areas is skincare. According to Nielsen's data in 2018 where skincare products are one of six categories of beauty products that have experienced an increase in sales from 2016 to 2017 by 9 percent.

In addition, based on the research results of Inventure and Alvara Research Center in 2020, it was stated that women tend to use skincare products compared to daily make-up during a pandemic because, during the COVID-19 pandemic, people were asked to wear masks for their daily activities. According to research by Inventure and Alvara Research Center in 2021, 54.9% of respondents use skincare products more regularly.

Fig. 1: Skincare Usage During the COVID-19 Pandemic

Source: Inventure and Alvara Research Center (2021)

Jakarta is one of the big cities in Indonesia which has a population of 10.61 million in 2021. It is recorded that the male population is 5.35 million, while the female population is recorded at 5.26 million. However, female population growth is higher than men where the growth in the number of women's population was 0.6% from the previous year which was 10.56 million people (Databoks, 2022). There are ten top cities in the Indonesian skincare market, namely Jakarta, Bekasi, Surabaya, Bandung, Jember, Medan, Tangerang, Semarang, Palembang, and Pekanbaru. Jakarta emerged as the city with the largest and first skincare market in Indonesia, followed by Bekasi and Surabaya (GlobalData, 2022). Thus it can be said that Jakarta is one of the big cities in Indonesia that has the potential to market beauty products to female consumers (women). Therefore this research will focus on female consumers located in Jakarta. In general, there are several brands of skincare products, both local and imported, in Indonesia. Although there are many imported skincare brands used in Indonesia,

local brands remain the choice of many Indonesians with affordable prices and good quality. The type of skincare that has the highest number of users in 2020 is day cream or face cream used in the morning or afternoon. This type of day cream skincare is used by 50.5 percent of female consumers during the pandemic.

Based on Top Brand Award data, Wardah's skincare brand has the second most memorable order (top of mind) and is the most preferred brand by consumers (Katadata, 2020). In addition, based on the Top Brand Index, Wardah's brand has a Top Brand Index of 38.5%. Wardah is a cosmetic product brand that won the top position in online sales in Indonesia in 2020 with a total of 7.37 million. The type of skincare that has the highest number of users in 2020 is day cream. Based on Top Brand Index data, three brands occupy the top positions in this type of face care product category, namely Pond's, Garnier, and Wardah's.

Fig. 2. Top Brand Index of Face Care Category Product

Source: Top Brand Index (2021)

From the data found, Wardah’s brand had the highest Top Brand Index in 2021. The increase in the percentage of Wardah's Top Brand Index could be due to the phenomenon of changes in consumer behavior during the pandemic that prefers to use skincare products over makeup and other factors that need to be explored more deeply. In general, it can be concluded that two beauty product brands that are Wardah's competitors, namely Pond's and Garnier. Based on data from Compass.id in 2021, the beauty brand Wardah received sales of IDR 13.4 billion on the marketplace in just 2 weeks with a total of 391,526 transactions (Compas, 2021). This beauty brand under Paragon Technology & Innovation Company also managed to generate revenue of around US\$214 million (around IDR 3.05 trillion) overall in 2020. This shows that Wardah’s brand cosmetic products are in great demand. Therefore, this research will focus on the discussion of skin care products such as the day cream

brand Wardah’s.

Researcher have conducted a pre-survey of 40 adult women in March 2022 and described twenty factors that are expected to determine the decision to buy skincare products. From the results of pre-survey data processing, there are five top factors in determining skincare purchases, namely product benefit, product reliability, originality, product availability in the marketplace and ease/practicality of skincare product as shown in the following diagram.

Fig. 3: Factors That Influence the Purchase Decision of Skincare Products

Source: Pre-Survey Results (2022)

No.	Journal Mapping Results (Determining Factors for Using Day Cream Skincare)	Journal Mapping Results (Determining Factors for Using Day Cream Skincare)
1.	Brand Image	Product Benefit
2.	Beauty Vlogger	Product Reliability
3.	Availability in the Marketplace	Originality
4.	Product Quality	Availability in the Marketplace
5.	Price	Ease of Payment
6.	Halal Label	Product Composition
7.	Green Product	Halal Considerations
8.		Price
9.		Reviews from Beauty Vloggers
10.		Practicality
11.		Promotion
12.		Skincare Product Durability
13.		Attractive Packaging
14.		Product Variations
15.		Country of Origin
16.		Side Effects
17.		Popularity
18.		People Recommendations
19.		Ease of Finding Products
20.		Social Media

Table 1: Factors That Determine Skincare Products Usage

Source: Pre-Survey Data Processing Results (2022)

Based on the results of previous research mapping, the determinants in the purchase decision for skincare product were obtained, such as Brand Image, Beauty Vlogger, Availability in the Marketplace, Product Quality, Price, Consideration of Halal Label, and Green Product. Researchers need to re-test the factors of Brand Image, Beauty Vlogger, Availability in the Marketplace and the Green Product obtained from previous research mapping as the determining variable (X) and add a new variable, namely the product benefit factor from the pre-survey results.

According to Nurvia and Sarasati (2020) that Beauty Vlogger is a determining factor in purchase decision for a skincare product. Meanwhile, the results of Lamasi and Santoso's research (2022) state that brand image, promotion, and product quality are factors that determine the decision to purchase Wardah's skincare product. According to Okadiani et al. (2019), The Green Product factor is a determining factor for consumers in making a purchase decision for Sensatia Botanical skincare. Therefore, in this study researchers need to examine the factors of Brand Image (X1), Beauty Vlogger (X2), Availability in the Marketplace (X3), Green Product (X4), and Product Benefit (X5) as determining factor that influences the Purchase Decision (Y) of Wardah's skincare product in the Z and Y generations in the city of Jakarta.

II. THEORY REVIEW

A. Customer Decision Model

The consumer decision model, also known as the Engel-Blackwell-Miniard Model, which was first developed in 1968 by Engel, Kollat, and Blackwell, is continuously being revised and depicted. The model is formed from six points of the decision-making process: the emergence of a need, followed by information search, both internally and externally, alternative evaluation, purchase, consumption, and post-purchase evaluation. This purchase decision is influenced by three main factors; the first is the stimuli obtained from marketing efforts. Second, external environmental variables consist of culture, social class, the influence of other people, family and situation. Third, individual variables consist of consumer resources, motivation, knowledge, attitudes, personality, values, and lifestyle. The Consumer Decision Model is important in this research because it is used to explain purchase decision-making, both with complex and simple characteristics.

B. Brand Image

Brand image is consumers' understanding of the uniqueness of a product or company (Girsang et al., 2020). Widianingrum & Mani (2021) states that brand image is a representation of the overall perception of the brand which is formed from information and experience of the brand. Brand image is related to attitudes consisting of beliefs and preferences towards a brand.

Brand image is a set of beliefs, ideas, and impressions that a person has of a brand. That is the reason brands greatly influence consumer choices about which products they will buy or use (Lamasi & Santoso, 2022). According

to Chin et al., (2018) stated that brand image can contribute to company success when customers are willing to buy products or services at higher prices. Therefore, to form a memory that sticks with consumers, a good brand image must be known by consumers continuously. Furthermore, brand image will be stronger when brand associations are also strongly interrelated (Amron, 2018).

C. Beauty Vlogger

Ambarwati (2019) states that Beauty Vloggers are a medium for creating Electronic Word Of Mouth (EWOM) communications through videos that they upload to YouTube, where electronic word of mouth is a form of marketing communication that contains positive or negative statements made by potential customers. Beauty Vloggers have the same concept as bloggers, namely providing information and reviewing beauty products (Lifi Pratika et al., 2020). According to Nurvia & Sarasati (2020), a Beauty Vlogger is someone who makes tutorial videos, provides tips and tricks on using skin care products, provides reviews and recommendations for selecting skincare products and then they will upload their content on their YouTube channel or other social media to be displayed to their followers, viewers, or subscribers.

D. Availability in the Marketplace

The Marketplace presents products or merchandise from various stores with a wide selection of categories. According to Maharizka (2018), the marketplace has a significant influence on the purchase intention of consumers using the Sagara Volcanic Mud Mask in the city of Bandung. One of the factors driving the decision to purchase cosmetic products online is the availability of cosmetic products. Product availability is the wide variety of goods available that can make consumers more interested in making a purchase. Product availability is part of the marketing mix factor (Huda et al., 2018). The more complete a cosmetics shop or online shop is in providing a variety of types of products in a wide selection of variants, prices, and also brands, the more consumers will be interested in buying it.

E. Green Product

Green product is a product that can be recycled, use non-hazardous materials, and reduce environmental impacts (Supriadi et al., 2017). According to Rahmania et al., (2020), green products are products that are designed not to pollute the environment starting from their production, distribution, and consumption. In addition, it can be recycled free of chemicals and poisons and good for consumer use.

According to Ridwan et al., (2018) state that a green product, or what can be called an environmentally sound product is a product that is designed and processed in a way to reduce effects that can pollute the environment, both in the process of production, distribution and consumption. Green products can be interpreted as products that do not damage nature or the environment, using less toxic materials, packaging, and recycled materials that do not damage the world (Bukhari & Rana, 2017).

F. Product Benefit

Woodruff and Gardial (2002) state that product benefits are customers' understanding of what they want from a product or service, compared to the costs incurred. Benefits are the basis of most purchases where consumers will consider the functional benefits and emotional benefits of a product that are expected according to what they need and want (Pratiwi et al., 2019). The perceived benefits of a product are a combination of physical attributes, service attributes, and technical support related to the use of these products or services (Ayu & Kirana, 2013). Perceived benefits are the level at which users believe that by using a product offered, they will experience the benefits derived from using the product (Andryanto, 2016).

G. Purchase Decision

Lamasi & Santoso (2022) states that purchase decisions are consumer actions to form a reference among brands in groups that have many choices and buy the most preferred products. According to Rasyid & Karya (2020) states that purchasing decisions are a problem-solving approach in human activity to buy an item or service in fulfilling their wants and needs, which consists of identifying needs and desires, seeking information, evaluating alternative purchases, purchase decision, and behavior after purchase.

H. Thinking Framework

Based on previous theoretical and prior research, the framework on this research could be described as follows:

Fig. 4: Thinking Framework

Source: Theoretical Review

I. Hypothesis

The hypothesis in this research is:

H1: Brand Image has a positive and significant effect on Purchase Decision for Wardah's day cream skincare product.

H2: Beauty Vlogger has a positive and significant effect on Purchase Decision for Wardah's day cream skincare product.

H3: Availability in the Marketplace has a positive and significant effect on Purchase Decision for Wardah's day cream skincare product.

H4: Green Product has a positive and significant effect on Purchase Decision for Wardah's day cream skincare product.

H5: Product Benefit has a positive and significant effect on Purchase Decision for Wardah's day cream skincare product.

III. METHODOLOGY

The research was conducted to find out how significant the influence of Brand Image (X1), Beauty Vlogger (X2), Availability in the Marketplace (X3), Green Product (X4), and Product Benefit (X5), on Purchase Decision (Y) of Wardah’s day cream skincare product. The method used in answering the problem formulation above is an explanatory survey. The population in this study were young adult women who used skincare product specifically Wardah’s day cream product located in the city of Jakarta.

The sample is to find out based on non-probability sampling with a purposive sampling technique. The sampling technique used in this study was purposive sampling with the following conditions: (1) women who are located in the city of Jakarta; (2) users of Wardah’s day cream; (3) young adults, namely generation Z and millennials from 15-40 years old; (4) purchase Wardah’s day cream product at least once in six months.

In this research, 46 parameters who will be questioned so that the number of samples needed is 165 people with a calculation of $33 \times 5 = 165$. The data collection techniques used in this research are as follows: (1) collecting primary data using a structured interview technique in the form of a questionnaire given to users of the Wardah’s day cream product through the Google Form; (2) secondary data collection using literature study techniques from several sources. This research conducted hypothesis testing, namely testing the effect of independent variables on the dependent

variable using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) analysis using SmartPLS software.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Taking into account the limitations of the sample and research time, the data processing in this study will use Smart Partial Least Square (SmartPLS) software version 3.0. Data analysis using SmartPLS in this research went through stages starting from: (1) analysis of the outer model including Construct Validity and Reliability tests; (2) analysis of the inner model including evaluation of the R-square value, Path Coefficient, and Goodness of Fit Model testing; and (3) Hypothesis Testing.

A. Convergent Validity

The convergent validity test is carried out by looking at the loading factor value of each indicator against the construct. The loading factor limit or the cut value used in this study is 0.7. The PLS model is declared to have met convergent validity if the loading factor value is greater than 0.70. Apart from being based on the loading factor value of each indicator, convergent validity can also be tested based on the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) value of each construct. The PLS model is declared to have met convergent validity if the AVE value of each construct is greater than 0.5. Based on the table below, the loading factor values for all indicators are greater than 0.7 and the AVE values for all constructs are greater than 0.5. From the data above, it can be concluded that all indicators in each construct have met the required convergent validity criteria.

Variable	Indicator	Outer Loading	Cut Value	AVE	Status
Brand Image	BR1	0.750	0.70	0.603	Valid
	BR2	0.723	0.70		Valid
	BR3	0.831	0.70		Valid
	BR4	0.715	0.70		Valid
	BR5	0.752	0.70		Valid
	BR6	0.803	0.70		Valid
	BR7	0.850	0.70		Valid
Beauty Vlogger	BV1	0.830	0.70	0.690	Valid
	BV2	0.897	0.70		Valid
	BV3	0.759	0.70		Valid
Availability in the Marketplace	KTM1	0.774	0.70	0.558	Valid
	KTM2	0.748	0.70		Valid
	KTM3	0.723	0.70		Valid
	KTM4	0.743	0.70		Valid
Green Product	GP1	0.808	0.70	0.724	Valid
	GP2	0.858	0.70		Valid
	GP3	0.886	0.70		Valid
Product Benefit	MP1	0.811	0.70	0.582	Valid
	MP2	0.762	0.70		Valid
	MP3	0.776	0.70		Valid
	MP4	0.766	0.70		Valid
	MP5	0.737	0.70		Valid
	MP6	0.721	0.70		Valid
	MP7	0.793	0.70		Valid
	MP8	0.782	0.70		Valid
	MP9	0.714	0.70		Valid
Purchase Decision	KP1	0.816	0.70	0.584	Valid

	KP2	0.805	0.70		Valid
	KP3	0.772	0.70		Valid
	KP4	0.706	0.70		Valid
	KP5	0.785	0.70		Valid
	KP6	0.724	0.70		Valid
	KP7	0.734	0.70		Valid

Table 2: Validity Test Results

Source: Data Processing Results (2023)

B. Discriminant Validity

Discriminant validity testing is carried out to ensure that each concept of each latent variable is different from other variables. In this research, the discriminant validity test refers to the Fornell-Larcker Criterion Test. The model has

good discriminant validity if the AVE squared value of each exogenous construct (values on the diagonal) exceeds the correlation between the construct and other constructs (values under the diagonal). Fornell-Larcker Criterion Test results can be seen in the table below.

Variable	Brand Image	Beauty Vlogger	Availability in the Marketplace	Green Product	Product Benefit	Purchase Decision
Brand Image	0.776					
Beauty Vlogger	0.291	0.831				
Availability in the Marketplace	0.315	0.744	0.747			
Green Product	0.648	0.385	0.399	0.851		
Product Benefit	0.820	0.347	0.349	0.693	0.763	
Purchase Decision	0.689	0.371	0.385	0.701	0.905	0.764

Table 3: Fornell-Larcker Criterion Test Results

Source: Data Processing Results (2023)

Based on the results of the discriminant validity test in the table above, shows that two constructs have a square root value of AVE below the correlation value with other latent constructs. This means that the two constructs do not yet have good discriminant validity, so it is necessary to remove indicators.

There were nine indicators removed in this test, namely indicators BR6, MP1, MP2, MP3, MP5, MP7, MP8, KP1, and KP6. The results of retesting the Fornell-Larcker Criterion test can be seen in the table below.

Variable	Brand Image	Beauty Vlogger	Availability in the Marketplace	Green Product	Product Benefit	Purchase Decision
Brand Image	0.781					
Beauty Vlogger	0.292	0.830				
Availability in the Marketplace	0.305	0.740	0.747			
Green Product	0.635	0.386	0.397	0.851		
Product Benefit	0.761	0.329	0.359	0.597	0.790	
Purchase Decision	0.633	0.348	0.369	0.697	0.763	0.779

Table 4: Fornell-Larcker Criterion Test Results

Source: Data Processing Results (2023)

Based on the results of the discriminant validity test in the table above, shows that the AVE square root value for each construct is greater than the correlation between one construct and the other constructs in the model. From the AVE value, the constructs in the estimated model meet the discriminant validity criteria.

C. Reliability Test

The construct reliability test can be seen from Cronbach's Alpha value and the Composite Reliability value of each construct. The value of Cronbach's Alpha and composite reliability and what is recommended is greater than 0.7. Reliability test results on the Brand Image (X1), Beauty Vlogger (X2), Availability in the Marketplace (X3), Green Product (X4), Product Benefit (X5), and Purchase Decision (Y) have Cronbach's Alpha values between 0.706-0.897 or all of them are above 0.7. Then, the six variables are declared valid.

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	AVE
Brand Image	0.871	0.903	0.610
Beauty Vlogger	0.774	0.869	0.690
Availability in the Marketplace	0.738	0.835	0.558
Green Product	0.809	0.887	0.724
Product Benefit	0.700	0.833	0.624
Purchase Decision	0.838	0.885	0.607

Table 5: Reliability Test Results

Source: Data Processing Results (2023)

D. R-Square

The R-Square value/Coefficient of Determination shows how much the exogenous variables influence the endogenous variables. The R-Square value is zero (0) to one

(1). If the R-Square value gets closer to one (1), then the independent variables provide all the information needed to predict the variation of the dependent variable. R-Square value can be seen in the table below.

	R-Square	R-Square Adjusted
Purchase Decision	0.675	0.665

Table 6: R-Square Test Results

Source: Data Processing Results (2023)

From the table above, the R-Square value which shows the simultaneous influence of Brand Image, Beauty Vlogger, Availability in the Marketplace, Green Product, and Product Benefit on Purchase Decision is 0.675 with an Adjusted R-Square value of 0.665. This can be interpreted as the influence of Brand Image, Beauty Vlogger, Availability in the Marketplace, Green Product, and Product Benefit on Purchase Decision is 67.5%. This 67.5% value indicates a "strong/substantial" relationship category, while the remaining 32.5% of Purchase decision is influenced by

other variables that are not included in the variables examined in this study. Several other variables referring to previous research are perceived price, perceived quality, and country image.

E. F-Square

F-Square is used to find out whether endogenous latent variables are significantly influenced by exogenous latent variables. Based on data processing, the F-Square value is obtained as follows:

	F-Square	Effect Size
Brand Image → Purchase Decision	0.002	Small
Beauty Vlogger → Purchase Decision	0.000	Small
Availability in the Marketplace → Purchase Decision	0.001	Small
Green Product → Purchase Decision	0.230	Moderate
Product Benefit → Purchase Decision	0.373	Big

Table 7: F-Square Test Results

Source: Data Processing Results (2023)

Based on the table above, the f-Square value on the relationship between the 3 independent variables namely Brand Image, Beauty Vlogger, and Marketplace Availability with the Purchase Decision variable has a small effect size. Meanwhile, the Green Product variable has a moderate effect size, and Purchase Decision has a big effect size.

F. Q-Square

If Q-Square > 0 in the structural model, the model has predictive relevance. If Q-Square < 0 then the model is said to have less predictive relevance. Value change Q-Square on PLS affects the model tested experimentally proportional. Based on data processing, the Q Square value is obtained as follows.

	SSO	SSE	Q2
Purchase Decision	825.000	501.632	0.392

Table 8: Q-Square Test Results

Source: Data Processing Results (2023)

When processing data with SmartPLS blindfolding, the omission distance used is 8 so that the quotient between the number of cases and that number is not whole. Based on table 4.16 above, the Q-Square value is 0.392. Because the

value is greater than 0, the model has predictive relevance. This means that the model is feasible to predict variable Y with reduced respondent data.

G. Path Coefficient

Path coefficients are used to see the hypothesized relationships between constructs. As previously stated, the path coefficient values range from -1 to +1, where values close to +1 represent a strong positive relationship, and path

coefficient values of -1 indicate a strong negative relationship. Although values close to +1 or -1 are almost always statistically significant, standard errors must be obtained using bootstrapping to test for significance.

Variable	Original Sample (O)	P Values
Brand Image -> Purchase Decision	-0.041	0.625
Beauty Vlogger → Purchase Decision	0.016	0.839
Availability in the Marketplace → Purchase Decision	0.021	0.788
Green Product → Purchase Decision	0.376	0.000
Product Benefit → Purchase Decision	0.558	0.000

Table 9: Path Coefficient Test Results

Source: Data Processing Results (2023)

The path coefficient values that can be seen in the original sample column range from -0.041 to 0.558. From this, it can be concluded that there is one path that has a negative relationship because it has a value away from +1 and there are four paths that have a positive relationship because it has a value close to +1.

H. Goodness of Fit Model

The fit of the PLS model can be seen from the Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR) value. As previously explained, the PLS model is declared to have fulfilled the goodness of fit model criteria if the SRMR value is < 0.10, and the model is declared a perfect fit if the SRMR value is < 0.08.

Variabel	Saturated Model	Estimated Model	rms Theta
SRMR	0.090	0.090	0.173
d ULS	2.419	2.419	
d G	1.048	1.048	
Chi-Square	882.839	882.839	
NFI	0.648	0.648	

Table 10: Goodness of Fit Model Test Results

Source: Data Processing Results (2023)

The results of the PLS Model Goodness of Fit test in the table above show that the saturated model's SRMR value is 0.090. Because the SRMR value is less than 0.10, this PLS model is declared to have fulfilled the goodness of fit model criteria so that the model is feasible to use. Additionally, rms Theta is a (conservative) threshold value, for rms Theta the value is 0.173 meaning it meets the criteria of less than 0.12.

I. Hypothesis

Based on the test results, if the path coefficient is positive, the p-value <0.05, and the T statistic > 1.96 then the hypothesis is accepted and it is concluded that exogenous variables have a positive effect on endogenous variables. From the results of the PLS model estimation using the bootstrapping technique, all paths are significant with a T statistic >1.96.

Variable	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
Brand Image → Purchase Decision	-0.041	-0.041	0.085	0.489	0.625
Beauty Vlogger → Purchase Decision	0.016	0.012	0.079	0.203	0.839
Availability in the Marketplace → Purchase Decision	0.021	0.027	0.077	0.269	0.788
Green Product → Purchase Decision	0.376	0.373	0.075	5.047	0.000
Product Benefit → Purchase Decision	0.558	0.561	0.086	6.517	0.000

Table 11: Goodness of Fit Model Test Results

Source: Data Processing Results (2023)

From the table above, several things are explained as follows:

- The magnitude of the T statistic for the Brand Image variable is 0.489 (smaller than 1.96) and the P values are 0.625 (greater than 0.05), meaning that Brand Image does not significantly influence the purchase decision.
- The magnitude of the T statistic for the Beauty Vlogger variable is 0.203 (smaller than 1.96) and the P values are 0.839 (greater than 0.05), meaning that the Beauty Vlogger does not significantly influence the purchase decision.
- The magnitude of the T statistic for the Availability in the Marketplace variable is 0.269 (smaller than 1.96) and the

P values are 0.788 (greater than 0.05), meaning that the Availability in the Marketplace does not significantly influence the purchase decision.

- The magnitude of the T statistic for the Green Product variable is 5.047 (greater than 1.96) and the P values are 0.000 (smaller than 0.05), meaning that the Green Product does significantly influence the purchase decision.
- The magnitude of the T statistic for the Product Benefit variable is 6.517 (greater than 1.96) and the P values are

0.000 (smaller than 0.05), meaning that the Product Benefit does significantly influence the purchase decision.

J. SEM Model Development

The theoretical model created at the hypothesis stage is described in the SEM model diagram which makes it easy to see the relationships causation to be tested. In this diagram, the relationship between constructs is indicated by arrows. Straight arrows indicate direct causality between one construct and another.

Fig. 5: SEM Model Development

Source: Data Processing Results (2023)

K. Discussion

The research hypothesis (H1) states that Brand Image has a positive and significant effect on the purchase decision. However, the results indicate that Brand Image has no significant effect on Purchase Decision. This means that Wardah's brand image does not encourage consumers to buy skincare product of the day cream type. This research is relevant to Putri et al. research, (2019) where in her research it was found that the brand image variable did not significantly influence the decision to purchase La Tulipe cosmetic products. This is because some consumers do not make the brand image a major consideration in a purchase decision. It can be concluded that the brand image of Wardah's brand skincare product is not the main thing that consumers consider when buying skincare product.

The research hypothesis (H2) states that the Beauty Vlogger has a positive and significant effect on the purchase decision. However, the results indicate that the Beauty Vlogger has no significant effect on the purchase decision. This means that the Beauty Vlogger used by Wardah's management for day cream product has not been able to increase individual decisions about using Wardah's day cream skincare product. Because Wardah's management

uses many artists as Beauty Vloggers. Whereas the Beauty Vlogger that Wardah's consumers want are experts in the field of skin and beauty. The results of this study are in line with research conducted by Malini (2021) on Emina brand lipstick product, where the results of his research stated that Beauty Vlogger did not have a significant effect on purchase decision for Emina brand lipstick product. Because of Beauty Vlogger's credibility is a determining factor for individuals (consumers) to use Emina brand lipstick product. This research is not in line with Nurvia and Sarasati's research (2020) that Beauty Vlogger has a significant influence on the decisions of female students in Bekasi in buying skin care products. Likewise, the results of research by Rasyid and Karya (2020) stated that Beauty Vlogger had a significant positive effect on purchase decision for Innisfree skincare product.

The research hypothesis (H3) states that Availability in the Marketplace has a positive and significant effect on the purchase decision. However, the results indicate that the Availability in the Marketplace has no significant effect on purchase decision. This means that the availability of skincare product in several marketplaces has not been able to increase individual decisions to buy skincare product. For

this reason, Wardah's management needs to look for the main determining factors for consumers in using Wardah's brand skincare product. The results of this study are by the research of Situngkir, et.al (2021) which states that the availability of beauty products does not affect consumer purchase decision. However, based on the research results of Yulianti, et.al (2021) the availability of products in various marketplaces has a significant influence on the purchase of products.

The research hypothesis (H4) states that the Green Product has a positive and significant effect on the purchase decision. The results indicate that the Green Product has a positive and significant effect on purchase decision. This means that products that have environmentally friendly ingredients (do not contain chemicals) can increase individual decisions about using skincare products. For this reason, Wardah's management needs to check the materials of Wardah's day cream product for hazardous chemicals such as mercury. Indonesian consumers don't want harmful products. The results of this study are relevant to research conducted by Okadiani, et.al (2019) which states that Green Product has a significant effect on purchase decision for Sensatia Botanicals skincare product. This is also supported by the research results of Hasanah and Handayani (2020) which state that Green Product for skincare product are a determining factor in deciding to use skincare product at Palapa Toserba Surabaya. This is in line with Dianti & Paramita's research (2021) which states that the effect of green product is positive and significant on the purchase decision of young consumers. However, the results of this study refute Suroto's research, et.al (2018) which states that Green Product has no significant influence on consumer satisfaction with The Body Shop products in Manado Town Square.

The research hypothesis (H5) states that the Product Benefit has a positive and significant effect on the purchase decision. The results indicate that the Product Benefit has a positive and significant effect on purchase decision. This means that Wardah's management needs to increase the benefits of day cream products in the form of emotional benefits as follows (1) increase self-confidence because they have a healthy face; (2) increase happiness/satisfaction; (3) increase self-admiration. The results of this study are following the research of Pratiwi, et. al (2019) states functional and emotional benefits have a significant influence on purchase decision for The Body Shop beauty products. Other studies that support the results of this study are Yolanda and Soesanto (2017) which state that perceived benefits have a significant influence on the decision to purchase Wardah's cosmetic products. According to Nguyen (2021) that the element of product benefits/benefits has a positive and significant influence on the intention to shop for cosmetics online.

V. CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

A. Conclusion

Based on the results of the discussion above, the following conclusions are obtained:

- Brand Image has no significant effect on purchase decision for Wardah's day cream skincare product. This means the purchase of Wardah's day cream skincare product is not determined by the brand image factor.
- Beauty Vlogger has no significant effect on purchase decision for Wardah's day cream skincare product. This is because the credibility of the Beauty Vlogger used by Wardah's management is not to the wishes of Wardah's consumers. Because consumers want Beauty Vloggers who come from skin and beauty experts (doctors).
- Availability in the Marketplace does not significantly influence the decision to purchase Wardah's day cream product. This is because availability on the Marketplace is not a determining factor in purchase Wardah's day cream skincare product.
- Green Product has a positive and significant influence on purchase decision for Wardah's day cream skincare product. This means that environmentally friendly products in the form of materials that do not contain harmful chemicals are the main determinant for consumers to use Wardah's day cream skincare product.
- Product Benefit has a positive and significant influence on purchase decision for Wardah's day cream skincare product. This means that skincare products that provide high emotional benefits in the form of increased self-confidence because they have a healthy face are a determining factor in using skincare product.

B. Suggestion

This research has two suggestions, namely (1) For Academics / further researchers; (2) For Practical advice. A more detailed explanation of the advice could be seen as follows:

- The researcher suggests further researchers examine skincare products imported from Korea because the interest of the Indonesian people is quite high in Korean culture. In addition, based on the conclusions above, the researcher suggests for future researchers to re-test this research model at different locations and examine other variables. Given the R-square value in this study of 0.675, it means that the decision to use day cream is determined by Brand Image, Beauty Vlogger, Availability in the Marketplace, Green Product, and Product Benefit.
- Based on the above conclusions, the researchers propose corrective actions or enhancements to the decision to purchase Wardah's brand day cream product using Wardah's management needs to increase emotional benefits for users of Wardah's day cream product in the form of emotional benefits in increasing self-confidence because they have a healthy face. So Wardah's management needs to reposition a strategy in the form of "skincare products can increase individual confidence because they have healthy skin."
- In addition, Wardah's management needs to continue to ensure that Wardah's day cream skincare product materials are protected from harmful chemicals such as

mercury. Because Indonesian consumers want products that do not contain harmful chemicals to use and do not damage the environment.

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